

Optical properties of ZnS, MgF₂, Ta₂O₅, Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ deposited by electron beam evaporation. A focus on their use as Anti-reflective Coatings

Brian Li^{1,2}, Mercedes Gabás¹, Efraín Ochoa³, Víctor González de la Cruz⁴, Mari Cruz López-Escalante⁴, Laura León-Reina⁴, Rafael Peña⁵, Pilar Garcia-Diaz⁵, Iván García¹ and Carlos Algora¹

¹ Instituto de Energía Solar, ETSI Telecomunicación, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid (SPAIN)

² Micro & Nanotechnology Lab, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

³ Adolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

⁴ Universidad de Málaga, Departamento de Física Aplicada, Departamento de Ingeniería Química y SCAI, Málaga (SPAIN)

⁵ Universidad de Alcalá, Departamento de Teoría de la Señal y Comunicaciones, Alcalá de Henares, Spain

1 Introduction (need to proofread)

Anti-reflective coatings (ARCs) are used in photonics to ensure that most of the optical energy is transmitted over a wavelength band of interest. They are used primarily in solar cells, semiconductor optical amplifiers, semiconductor lasers, master oscillator power amplifiers, etc. ARCs range from single-wavelength operation (for narrowband lasers) to coatings functioning over very broad spectral bands such as in the case of multi-junction solar cells (300–1800 nm).

ARCs are key for increasing the efficiency of solar cells by maximizing the solar light impinging on the active semiconductor layers, which means the maximization of light transmission [Algora1997]. Multi-junction solar cells (3 junctions and beyond), with their wide effective absorption spectrum, pose additional challenges for ARC design compared to single junction cells. For these cells, complex designs with multiple layers and different materials are often required to not only achieve good anti-reflection properties over the wide absorption spectrum, but also allow for effective current matching between the individual sub-cells. To effectively design and optimize ARCs on multi-junction cells, we must have a complete understanding of the optical and physical properties of different ARC materials. In this paper we focus on materials which are widely used as ARCs, namely, MgF₂, ZnS, Ta₂O₅, Al₂O₃ and TiO₂.

MgF₂ has been widely used as an ARC, not only in several types of photovoltaic panels [Sarkin2020], but also for solar thermal applications [Motamedi2019]. Several preparation techniques can give rise to good optical MgF₂ layers, the most common being electron beam evaporation [Dumas2000], or sol-gel coatings [Krüger2008]. Moreover, it can work as a monolayer, or in a bilayer structure [Sun2020]. ZnS is another material widely used in the design and growth of broadband ARCs [Krishna2017]. It is mainly proposed as a constituent of a multilayer, especially suited for III-V solar cells [Algora1997, Wang2012, Zhan2014, Bernal-Correa2015]. MgF₂/ZnS stacks have reached excellent optical performance by means of double layers, Herpin equivalent, etc.

[Herpin, Aiken]. A weak point of these materials for some applications is their instability (hygroscopic) and lack of adhesion. This is why more stable layers based on oxides such as Ta₂O₅, Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ are preferred for some uses [Dinjemans2012,]. Tantalum pentoxide (Ta₂O₅) is a high refractive index dielectric with chemical stability at high temperatures and a melting point of 1785 °C, and is thus suitable for high temperature applications. Aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) has become more popular for their high dielectric strength, exceptional stability, and durability against hostile environments, passivation properties, and high transparency down to 250 nm. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) has a high value of refractive index and exceptional chemical stability.

While data are available for the bulk optical properties of these materials in different sources or database, thin-films often have a different microstructure from bulk material, which can lead to variance in the optical properties. Additionally, the deposition method can impact the properties of these materials [Sarkin2020].

There are several methods for depositing these materials such as thermal evaporation, electron beam, atomic layer deposition, sputtering, etc. Depending on the specific application, material to be deposited, etc. one method can be selected. Electron Beam Physical Vapor Deposition (EBPVD) can evaporate high-purity layers of a wide pallet of dielectric materials including those of high melting point, making it an effective technique for the deposition of ARCs. In addition, EBPVD is one of the preferred techniques for ARC deposition in industrial settings.

For these reasons, in this work we have deposited MgF₂, ZnS, Ta₂O₅, Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ by EBPVD with the aim of characterizing their optical properties, which allow their proper use in optimized ARC designs. Their refractive index (n), extinction coefficient (k), and thickness (d) were determined over the absorption spectrum using spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE). In addition, the reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) of samples were measured over the spectrum with spectrophotometry. R and T values were then calculated from the ellipsometry-derived properties (both n and k) using the software *Optical* [Centurioni], and were compared to real measurements from spectrophotometry to evaluate the accuracy of the ellipsometry properties. Different thicknesses were deposited for all materials to determine how the degree of porosity that could impact their properties. The thickness selection was made by considering the typical optimum thicknesses if the materials are deposited alone or stacked with other materials onto solar cells. Oxide materials were deposited with varying levels of oxygen flow into the deposition chamber. Samples were then compared to determine the effects of these conditions on the optical properties. Finally, we present the impact on the calculation of optimum ARC thicknesses for GaInP/Ga(In)As/Ge solar cells depending on using the standard refractive indexes from literature (Sopra) or by using the real ones determined in this work.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Sample Preparation and Deposition

For this study, a Pfeiffer Classic 500 Twin EBPVD machine was used for e-beam deposition. The system has two chambers, one for metals and one for dielectrics, each containing six pockets for different materials. A SQC-310 Thin Film Deposition Controller is used for automatic deposition control. In addition, the dielectric chamber of the Classic 500 allows for oxygen flow into the chamber, which is controlled through a PR 4000B mass flow controller. For oxide materials, the bonds between the oxygen and cations can be broken during the evaporation process, and oxygen is often injected in a process known as reactive evaporation. This process allows oxide materials to maintain their stoichiometric properties by replacing oxygen atoms lost during evaporation. The nominal deposition rate was 1 Å/s for all materials, so the current of the e-gun was automatically adjusted as follows: 1-3 mA for both ZnS and MgF₂, 45 mA for Al₂O₃, 75 mA for Ta₂O₅ and 95 mA for TiO₂. In the case of ZnS and MgF₂, we observed an initial overshoot in the deposition rate at the beginning of each evaporation which decreased afterwards.

Tested materials were simultaneously deposited onto two different substrates: p-type silicon wafers and glass. The substrate surfaces were cleaned prior to material layer deposition. Glass substrates surfaces were cleaned using lab soap and water, then blow-dried with nitrogen. Silicon samples were first cleaned with acetone and methanol to remove organic residue and particles. Then, they were agitated for 3 minutes in a HF:H₂O (1:6) solution to remove the upper silicon oxide layer from the surface. Lastly, they were agitated in deionized water to remove the HF solution, and blow-dried with nitrogen.

After cleaning, substrates were mounted onto holder plates, and placed into the dielectric chamber. A piece of kapton tape was also placed on one end of each sample to form a step-edge for profilometry thickness testing. This allows us to have a first thickness estimation to be used as input data for the ellipsometric fitting (see below). For each deposition, two silicon samples and one glass sample were used. For each type of dielectric material multiple films were deposited at varying thickness and (for oxides) oxygen flow rates by means of tens of EBPVD processes. Before deposition, the chamber was pumped down to a pressure of $2 - 2.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar. In addition, sample substrates were unheated during deposition, and there was no post-deposition annealing of samples.

Silicon samples were used to attain optical properties and thickness of the dielectrics from ellipsometry, while glass samples were used to characterize reflectance and transmittance of the films with spectrophotometry.

2.2 Sample Characterization

Spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE) is a highly sensitive method for determining the complex refractive index and thickness of both bulk and thin-film materials as a function of wavelength. The method is based on the polarization change of light reflected from the material surface with respect to the incident light. This polarization change depends on the optical and structural properties of the material, thus allowing these properties to be determined. The measured data for polarization change is given by two angles, Ψ and Δ , which describe the changes in the relative amplitude ratio and phase difference of the

parallel and perpendicular components (p and s, respectively) of the reflected wave. These two components are related by the formula:

$$\rho = r_p/r_s = \tan(\Psi) \exp(i\Delta) \quad (1)$$

Where r_p and r_s are the reflection coefficients of the p and s components of the wave. Spectroscopic ellipsometers measure the parameters Δ and Ψ as a function of wavelength. Since SE is an indirect measurement method, the physical and optical properties of the deposited film cannot be calculated directly from this data. Rather, an appropriate optical model of the film must be created, and subsequently fitted to the measured Δ and Ψ data by adjusting the properties of the model. An example of such a model and subsequent fitting can be seen in the Supplementary material file for an Al₂O₃ sample (Figure S1). Fitting outputs are the deposited film refractive index as a function of wavelength, as well as the film thickness, d . The refractive index n , extinction coefficient k , and thickness d of the thin-film samples were determined using SE with a Sopra GES-5 Ellipsometer. Ψ and Δ were measured on silicon samples in the wavelength range from 180–1699 nm, and the software SEA (Semilab) was used for subsequent ellipsometry modeling and analysis. In addition, SEA was used to extrapolate the resulting calculations in the 1700-1800 nm range, since the ellipsometer was not able to measure in this range. This was done with the aim of the optimization of broadband III-V multijunction solar cells done in Section 3.6.

The surface of the deposited films was monitored using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Planar view and cross-section images were taken with a FEI Helios Nanolab 650 Dual Beam microscope.

The samples surface composition was analyzed using X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS), using a Thermo Scientific Multilab 2000 spectrometer fitted with a dual-anode X-ray source (Mg-K α and Al-K α with photon energies 1253.6 and 1486.7 eV, respectively), and a 110 mm hemispherical sector analyzer. Detailed core level spectra were measured using both X-ray sources. All the measurements were made on as-received samples i.e. no Ar⁺ sputtering cleaning was done. The core level spectra were fitted using the XPSpeak software package [XPSpeak] and the commercial CasaXPS software UNIFIT 2009 [UNIFIT].

X-ray Reflectometry (XRR) (Laura está en ello)

Since n , k , and d were obtained from modeling, we wanted to confirm the accuracy of these parameters with a direct measurement technique. For this purpose, the reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) of each film was measured using spectrophotometry. R and T measurements were made on the glass samples using a LAMBDA 1050 UV/Vis/NIR Spectrophotometer in the range from 299 –1799nm. Then, the thin-film simulation software *Optical* [Centurioni2005] was used to create a model of each film using the ellipsometry-attained parameters, and subsequently calculate the reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) over the wavelength range of 300-1800nm.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 MgF₂

[Table 1](#) briefly describes the MgF₂ deposited films. The films were evaporated with 4 different nominal thicknesses (3, 30, 100, 200 nm). In addition, since MgF₂ films can absorb water when exposed to air, especially at low deposition rates and low temperature [Hass1982], samples for each film thickness were stored for a period ranging from 2 to 13 days in two different atmospheres, air and nitrogen, to determine if the optical properties would be affected by water absorption. However, when the raw Ψ and Δ measurements were compared for samples of equal thickness stored in air and nitrogen, there was negligible difference in the measurements for all samples tested. Therefore, further analysis and data fitting was carried out only on the samples exposed to air for simplicity. Table 1 gathers nominal thickness and modeled thickness from ellipsometry for these samples.

Table 1: Deposited MgF₂ samples

Sample #	Nominal d (nm)	Ellipsometry d (nm)
MgF2_1	3	7.1
MgF2_2	30	31.4
MgF2_3	100	97.9
MgF2_4	200	182.4

The ellipsometry data were fitted using a Cauchy Law to model the refractive index, n , of MgF₂ samples. The imaginary part of the complex refractive index, k , was assumed to be null over tested range based on previous reporting of MgF₂ values in Sopra database. A good fitting was achieved for all the samples using such conditions, therefore the model was not complicated any further with non-zero k values. Figure shows the refractive index values for MgF₂ samples over the range of thicknesses after fitting, as well as index values for bulk MgF₂ from the Sopra database in the range from 234 nm to 953 nm. The samples of nominal 30 nm, 100 nm, and 200 nm thickness were very close to the Sopra database values, while the 3 nm sample had index values offset upwards from the other samples.

Figure 1: Spectral refractive indexes of MgF₂ samples as a function of thickness. Pink, red, blue and green symbols account for MgF₂_1, MgF₂_2, MgF₂_3 and MgF₂_4 (see Table 1) refractive indexes, respectively. Database values are the black crosses.

Differences in refractive index values between the thinnest sample and the rest of the samples can be explained regarding XPS results. According to XPS and to ellipsometry results, thicker samples composition would be mostly the targeted one, i.e. MgF₂ (see Supplementary Material, Figure S3). However, for the thinnest sample (3 nm), several Mg compounds contributions have been found in the Mg 2p core level (Figure 2). Experimental data have been recorded for two take-off angles 30° (Figure 4 left) and 90° (Figure 2 right), in such a way that for the last angle, explored depth doubles that of the first one. In both cases, assuming a MgF₂ film thickness around 5 nm (as an average between the nominal one of 3 nm and the fitting one by SE of 7.1 nm), part of the photoelectrons giving rise to Mg2p core level data are coming from interface between MgF₂ and substrate, but for take-off angle 90°, their contribution to the Mg2p signal is higher. Apart from Mg fluoride, Mg oxides and hydroxides fingerprints are visible after data fitting. Surprisingly, the amount of these two compounds increases as the analyzed depth does, going from 22% of the global signal for 30° take-off angle data, to 33% for the data recorded at 90°. Since the thickness of this sample is very small, this fact strongly suggests the origin of such contamination is on the interface between substrate and deposited layer. That is, those compounds are formed at the initial stages of layer growth, involving ambient O atoms and those removed from the silicon substrate surface due to electron impinging.

Figure 2: Mg 2p core level signal deconvolution for the thinnest sample MgF2_1 (3 nm). Left picture corresponds to data taken at 30° take-off angle, while right picture is for the data taken at 90° take-off angle.

Regarding these XPS results, differences in refractive index between the thinnest sample and the rest of them can be explained in terms of the different layer composition, since for the first sample at least 25-30% of sample volume does not correspond to the nominal composition MgF₂. The formation of MgO would increase the sample refractive index (~1.8) due to its higher value for the Mg oxide, as compared to the Mg fluoride one (~1.38). For the rest of the samples, a small amount of Mg oxides and hydroxides (about 10% of sample volume) has also been detected in XPS analysis (see Supplementary material), and it is probably the reason for the small deviations of the refractive index values for these samples as compared to the database values. It is important to note that in the MgF₂/ZnS double ARC, a MgF₂ adherence layer of about 3-5 nm is usually deposited onto the semiconductor solar cell prior to the ZnS layer [ref]. Therefore, the impact of this significant difference in refractive index for the 3-5 nm layer when optimizing the double ARC will be assessed at the end of this paper.

Validation of the refractive indexes obtained (Figure 1) after the fitting of the ellipsometric data has been achieved using reflectance and transmittance measurements. For all the MgF₂ samples the match between experimental and simulated reflectance and transmittance is very good. Figure 3 shows the comparison for the samples with 3 and 100 nm of MgF₂ as representative cases of extreme thicknesses. Therefore, our refractive indexes reflect the optical properties of the EBPVD prepared MgF₂ films according to their thickness.

Figure 3. Comparison between both experimental reflectance and transmittance data and the simulated functions calculated from the refractive indexes of Figure 1 for 3 and 100 nm MgF₂ samples

3.2 ZnS

Table 2 presents the deposited ZnS samples, along with the modeled thicknesses for comparison. The substrates were initially deposited with an MgF₂ adhesion layer of a 3 nm (nominal), and afterwards ZnS layers were deposited with 4 different nominal thicknesses (5, 20, 50, 100nm).

Table 2: Deposited ZnS samples with nominal and modeled thicknesses

Sample	Nominal d (nm)	Ellipsometry d (nm)	Ellipsometry MgF ₂ adhesion layer (nm)
ZnS_1	5	3.3	10.8
ZnS_2	20	19.6	6.5
ZnS_3	50	52	3.3
ZnS_4	100	100.8	4.2

Figure 4 gives the calculated n and k values for the ZnS samples, as well as the Sopra database values for comparison. Experimental values were calculated using an Adachi dispersion model, combining several oscillators to simulate interband transitions [Adachi1999]. The sample values matched closely to the Sopra values. In the high wavelength range, there was a general trend of increasing refractive index as thickness decreased, though the values for wavelengths greater than 400 nm are always smaller than Sopra database values. This trend changes for wavelengths lower than 400 nm. On the other hand, the extinction coefficient values do not show a clear trend as a function of film thickness.

Figure 4: Complex refractive index values for ZnS samples. Left: refractive index n ; right: extinction coefficient k . Red dots for 20 nm are hidden since they overlap beneath the 50 nm green dots. For both graphics, legend notations correspond to those of Table 2.

Figure 5 shows the Zn2p_{3/2} core level (left) and the S2p core level XPS analysis for the 50 nm thickness sample. Data were taken at 90° take-off angle. In both cases, a unique contribution compatible with ZnS composition fits the experimental signal. The same results have been obtained when analyzing data from the thinnest sample ZnS_1 (5 nm) as well as for the thickest ones. That is, there are no spurious phases containing neither Zn nor S in the layers. These results are supported also by EDS analysis taken on sample ZnS_4 (see supplementary material file).

Figure 5: Zn2p_{3/2} (left) and S2p (right) core level signals for ZnS_3 sample (50 nm). Black line corresponds to experimental data and red line is the data fit. Blue line in right figure is the XPS signal background. Experimental data were taken at 90° take-off angle in order to maximize the explored depth.

However, there is some contamination related with C and O compounds on sample surfaces, which is typical after air exposure. Besides, for the thinnest sample, ZnS_1, whose estimated thickness is smaller than 5 nm, the XPS O1s signal indicates contamination which is not seen for the thicker sample (see Figure S5), and its origin is probably in the interface between MgF₂ adhesion layer and the ZnS layer. The presence

of these two contaminants on the sample surface and of O at the interface between MgF₂ and ZnS layers is possibly the reason for the smaller refractive indexes for wavelengths greater than 400 nm than those corresponding to the Sopra database. Since thinner layer thickness leads to a greater difference between database and layer refractive indexes, the greater amount of contaminants as compared to layer bulk mass for thinner samples would support this hypothesis.

Again, the comparison between experimental reflectance and transmittance of the samples, and the simulations made from the refraction indexes obtained after ellipsometry analysis allow us to validate these last data. As shown by Figure 6, an exemplary case of all ZnS samples, the match is very good along the whole spectrum.

Figure 6. Comparison between experimental reflectance and transmittance data and the simulated functions calculated from the refractive indexes of Figure 4 for ZnS₃ (50 nm). MgF₂ adhesion layer is included in the simulations.

3.3 Ta₂O₅

Table 3 presents the Ta₂O₅ samples which were deposited at two different nominal thicknesses (20 nm and 60 nm), and with three different oxygen flow rates (0, 3.75 and 7 sccm), and also shows the modeled thicknesses from ellipsometry fitting for comparison. It should be noted that Ta₂O₅ is a very difficult material to melt by e-gun, which manifests itself in a certain thickness variation. In order to mitigate this variation, two depositions were performed for each condition of thickness and oxygen flow to evaluate the reproducibility of the process. Regarding this last point, we anticipate that no significant differences in optical behavior were found between these two depositions with same growth conditions.

Table 3: Deposited Ta₂O₅ samples with nominal and modeled (ellipsometry) thicknesses together with the oxygen flow used in their deposition process.

Sample	Oxygen flow (sccm)	Nominal d (nm)	Ellipsometry d (nm)
--------	--------------------	------------------	-----------------------

Ta2O5_1	0	60	63.6
Ta2O5_2	0	60	60.4
Ta2O5_3	3.75	60	59.3
Ta2O5_4	3.75	60	62.7
Ta2O5_5	7	60	66.2
Ta2O5_6	7	60	67.8
Ta2O5_7	0	20	21.3
Ta2O5_8	0	20	23.3
Ta2O5_9	3.75	20	20.6
Ta2O5_10	3.75	20	23.6
Ta2O5_11	7	20	22
Ta2O5_12	7	20	23.5

Figure 7 gives the calculated n and k values, respectively, for the odd-numbered Ta₂O₅ samples of Table 3. Sopra values are shown only for n since the Sopra database gave values of $k = 0$ over the wavelength range of 300-850 nm. A Sellmeier dispersion model was used to calculate these index values. As seen in Figure 7 left, the 60 nm samples for all oxygen flow rates had a consistently higher refractive index than the 20 nm samples for wavelengths greater than 300 nm and that the refractive index gap increases with wavelength. In contrast, the oxygen flow itself had a small effect on refractive index for a given thickness, with the samples deposited with 3.75 sccm having lower refractive indexes, while the samples with 7 sccm of oxygen exhibited higher indexes, no matter the thickness. Extinction coefficient values, as seen in Figure 7 right, were very consistent between samples, and there was not a noticeable trend for either thickness or oxygen flow rate. For wavelengths higher than around 300 nm, $k = 0$ in agreement with the Sopra database.

Figure 7: Refractive index (left) and extinction coefficient (right) for Ta₂O₅ samples of Table 3.

In order to clarify the optical behavior of these samples, XPS and XRR measurements have been conducted. XPS analysis has shed some light on the layers composition. Two samples, both 60 nm thick, deposited with and without 3.75 sccm O₂ flux, and a third one, 20 nm thick, deposited with 3.75 sccm O₂ flux have been analyzed. Samples deposited with the same O₂ flux (although with different thicknesses of 20 and 60 nm) have the same composition, according to the identical Ta4f and O1s core levels that have been recorded for both of them. On the contrary, for the sample deposited without O₂ flux, an important contribution from a Ta sub-oxide is customary to fit the XPS experimental data (Figure 8), which suggests the layer composition is not only Ta₂O₅, at least for the upper part of the layer. On the contrary, for the samples deposited with 3.75 sccm O₂ flux, Ta₂O₅ contribution fits perfectly the experimental signal. Therefore, a certain O₂ flux seems to be necessary to achieve targeted composition for these layers.

Figure 8: Ta4f core level signal corresponding to the Ta₂O₅_1 without oxygen flow (left) and Ta₂O₅_3 with 3.75 sccm oxygen flow (right) samples. Both are 60 nm thickness. Black lines correspond to the measured signals, while red line corresponds to Ta₂O₅ contribution and blue line corresponds to a Ta sub-oxide contribution. Experimental data were taken at 90° take-off angle in order to maximize the explored depth.

However, despite obtaining proper composition (Ta₂O₅) for the layers deposited with 3.75 sccm O₂ flux, the refractive indexes obtained from ellipsometry measurements are higher than the Sopra database one. XRR data analysis helps to clarify this point (Figure 9). The same two samples measured by XPS with different thickness deposited with 3.75 sccm O₂ flux have been measured. The obtained results indicate that, in both cases, layer density is smaller than the nominal Ta₂O₅ value of 8.2 gr/cm³. More precisely, for the 20 nm thick sample, density is 7.5 gr/cm³, while for the 60 nm thick sample is even smaller, 6.5 gr/cm³ with a very thin sublayer on top of it, whose density is 5 gr/cm³. These results would explain the refractive index differences between thick and thin samples showed in Figure 7, and the fact that the thin sample's optical behavior is more similar to that showed in the database, since the thinner samples density is closer to the standard one. The same

trend of increasing refractive index when increasing the thickness of deposited tantalum oxide layers was found in [Atanasova].

Figure 9: XRR signal (dark blue) and data fit (light blue) corresponding to samples Ta2O5_3 (60 nm thick, left) and Ta2O5_9 (20 nm thick, right). Both samples were deposited with 3.75 sccm O₂ flow.

The reason for the different density values measured for these layers could be related with a fact detected in EDS experiments. As it is shown in the supplementary material file (Figure S6), the mean ratio O/Ta reaches a value of 3.6 for the thicker samples, while for the thinner samples, it is a bit higher than 2.5. That would explain the smaller layer density found for the thicker samples.

Again, the comparison between experimental reflectance and transmittance of the samples, and the simulations made from the refraction indexes obtained after ellipsometry analysis allow to validate these last data, since, as it is shown in Figure 10, the match is very good along the whole spectrum for all samples no matter thickness nor oxygen flow.

Figure 10. Comparison between experimental both reflectance and transmittance data and the simulated functions calculated from the refractive indexes of Figure 7 for Ta₂O₅ layers with thicknesses of 20 and 60 nm and for 0, 3,75 and 7 sccm oxygen flow.

3.4 Al₂O₃

Table 4 below describes the Al₂O₃ samples, which were deposited at 3 different thicknesses (20, 50, 100 nm) and 2 different oxygen flow rates (0, 4 sccm), and also shows the modeled thickness by ellipsometry for comparison. The differences experienced between nominal and modelled thicknesses for samples with 20 and 50 nm are attributed to non-optimal calibration of the sensor tooling factor which was improved for the 100 nm samples.

Table 4: Deposited Al₂O₃ samples with nominal and modeled thicknesses

Sample	Oxygen flow (sccm)	Nominal d (nm)	Ellipsometry d (nm)
Al ₂ O ₃ _A	0	20	28
Al ₂ O ₃ _B	4	20	30.6
Al ₂ O ₃ _C	0	50	61.2
Al ₂ O ₃ _D	4	50	66.7
Al ₂ O ₃ _AA	0	100	102.5
Al ₂ O ₃ _BB	4	100	108.9

Figure 11 gives the n values for all Al_2O_3 samples and from the Sopra database. A Cauchy dispersion model was used to attain these values. k was assumed to be 0 based on reported literature values, and therefore, is not given in this section. As seen in Figure 11, the refractive index values at high wavelength tended to increase with sample thickness in the visible and IR wavelength ranges, as has been stated in [Etinger-Geller2019] for samples grown by Atomic Layer Deposition. Values achieved for 50 and 100 nm thick samples match with some previous results for samples with similar thickness [Shamala2004, Etinger-Geller2019]. In addition, the oxygen flow itself seemed to have a rather small effect on the sample's optical properties.

Figure 11: Refractive index values for Al_2O_3 samples of Table 4.

In order to understand the ellipsometry results, further characterization has been accomplished for these layers. SEM images reveal a rather dirty sample surface (see figure S7 in the supplementary material file), no matter the layer thickness nor O_2 flow during growth. Besides, the EDS analysis indicates that the mean O/Al ratio is much higher than the corresponding value for Al_2O_3 composition, i.e. 1.5, for any of these samples (see figure S8 in supplementary material file). However, there are some differences among samples that are worth mentioning here. O/Al ratio reaches values as high as 4.9 and 4.6 for the thinner samples, while for the thicker layers this value diminishes to 3.7 and 3.5, for the samples deposited without and with O_2 flux, respectively. We must take into account that in these EDS analyses, Si is always the most abundant detected element (see Table in Figure S8 in the supplementary material file). That is, these analyses are probing the whole aluminum oxide sample thickness. Therefore, we are estimating the mean O and Al amounts along the layer thickness. From these figures, it is evident that sample composition is not just Al_2O_3 .

XPS analysis corroborates this. Figure 12 shows the deconvolution of the Al 2p core level signal for the Al₂O₃_A and Al₂O₃_AA samples, i.e. the 20 nm and the 100 nm thickness samples, both deposited without O₂ flow. Two different contributions were needed to fit XPS signal for all the samples, which account for two different Al environments in the layer. According to their binding energies and the information presented in the former paragraph, an Al hydroxide coexists with Al₂O₃ in the samples. The amount of this Al hydroxide in the layer is strongly dependent on thickness, being higher for the thinner samples, Al₂O₃_A and Al₂O₃_B. In Figure 12, the Al hydroxide contributions intensity is 74% of the global signal for the thinner sample (left), while it is 65% for the thicker sample (right). These figures should be representative of the hydroxide amount in the upper part of the deposited layers, since XPS explored depth is on the order of few nm. For the samples deposited with O₂ flow, the amount of Al hydroxides is always a bit higher when comparing with samples with the same thickness deposited without O₂ flow (not shown here). Formation of Al hydroxides on top of Al₂O₃ films exposed to air is a well-known and reported fact [Madaan2013].

Figure 12: Al₂p core level deconvolution corresponding to samples prepared without O₂ flow, 20 nm thick (left) and 100 nm thick (right).

Besides, XRR data analysis corresponding to the Al₂O₃_BB sample (not shown here), demonstrates that layer density, $2.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ gr/cm}^3$, is smaller than the nominal Al₂O₃ value, 3.95 gr/cm^3 . In fact, that value is much closer to the typical Al hydroxide value, 2.4 gr/cm^3 , which again supports our previous discussion. The higher Al hydroxide presence in thinner layers which results in a lower density is behind their smaller n values when compared with those of thicker layers.

Again, the appropriateness of the refractive index extracted from ellipsometry data is confirmed by the simulation of the sample's transmittance and reflectance and its comparison with experimental results. Figure 13 shows two exemplary cases of aluminum oxide samples with the thinner thickness without oxygen flow and the thicker sample with 4 sccm oxygen flow. As can be seen the match is very good along the whole spectrum.

Figure 13. Comparison between experimental both reflectance and transmittance data and the simulated functions calculated from the refractive indexes of Figure 11. Aluminum oxide sample of 20 nm without oxygen flow (left) and sample of 100 nm with 4 sccm oxygen flow (right).

3.5 TiO₂

Table 4 below describes the TiO₂ samples, which were deposited at 4 different nominal thicknesses (10, 20, 50, 100 nm) and 2 different oxygen flow rates (0 and 5 sccm), and also shows the modeled thicknesses for comparison.

Table 5: Deposited TiO₂ samples with nominal and modeled thicknesses

Sample	Oxygen flow (sccm)	Nominal d (nm)	Ellipsometry d (nm)
TiO ₂ _A	0	10	12.2
TiO ₂ _B	5	10	11.5
TiO ₂ _C	0	20	21.5
TiO ₂ _D	5	20	21.5
TiO ₂ _E	0	50	51.4
TiO ₂ _F	5	50	49.4
TiO ₂ _G	0	100	101.2
TiO ₂ _H	5	100	98.6

Figure 14 gives the n values for all TiO₂ samples and from the Sopra database. These values were calculated using a Tauc-Lorentz model. Figure 14 on the left gives a wide index range, and shows the large difference between the Sopra values and the measured sample values, while Figure 14 right gives a restricted index range to focus on the measured samples.

Figure 14: Refractive index values for all TiO₂ samples including the Sopra value (left) and magnification for n ranging from 1.9 to 2.4 (right).

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. Figure 15 left and right plot the refractive index values of the 0 sccm and 5 sccm samples O₂ flow, respectively, allowing for comparison of the indexes as a function of thickness. In both cases, there was a trend of increasing refractive index with thickness in the high wavelength range for the 20, 50 and 100 nm samples. The thinnest sample (10 nm) exhibits a particular behavior showing the highest n values for the samples deposited without O₂ flow, while it has n values between the 20 nm and 50 nm samples for the samples deposited with 5 sccm O₂ flow.

Figure 15: Refractive index values for samples with 0 sccm (left) and 5 sccm (right) oxygen flow rates.

The reason for the discrepancies observed between the thinnest samples as compared to the rest of them is probably related to the Ti₂O₃ presence detected in the XPS analysis developed for these samples. As it is explained in the supplementary material file, the Ti2p core level signal is fitted with two contributions for all the samples, corresponding to Ti₂O₃ and TiO₂, the first oxide being the minority one (see Figure S9). The formation of such sub-oxides is a well-known fact when preparing TiO₂ layers by electron beam evaporation [Eiamchai2009]. However, the total amount of Ti₂O₃ in the thinnest samples is much higher than for the rest of them when considering the total sample volume as it

is explained in the Supplementary material file. Therefore, the contribution of this oxide to the layer refractive index is more important in the thinner samples. According to [Abdel-Aziz2006], the Ti_2O_3 refractive index is always higher than that of TiO_2 along the whole wavelength range measured in this work. For that reason, TiO_2_A and TiO_2_B refractive indexes do not follow the trend of increasing refractive index with thickness which is clearly showed in Figure 15.

Concerning the tendency of increasing n values with thickness (apart from the thinnest samples of 10 nm), EDS analysis may shed some light in order to explain it. As seen in Table 6, the O/Ti ratio is higher than 2 (which nominally corresponds to TiO_2), though it decreases as thickness increases. The lowest value is 2.7, which corresponds to the TiO_2_H sample, 100 nm thick and deposited with 5 sccm O_2 flow.

Table 6: O/Ti ratio for the TiO_2 samples, as calculated from EDS analysis.

Sample	O/Ti ratio
TiO_2_A	4.1
TiO_2_B	3.6
TiO_2_C	3.2
TiO_2_D	3.1
TiO_2_E	3
TiO_2_F	2.9
TiO_2_G	2.8
TiO_2_H	2.7

This high O/Ti ratio would explain the fact that the refractive index found for these samples is always smaller than the database, since the sample density would be lower than that corresponding to a completely packed TiO_2 layer. Besides, the decreasing tendency of O/Ti ratio with layer thickness, would imply an increasing layer density with thickness, and this would agree with the fact that the thicker the layer, the closer the refractive index values are to the database (except for the thinnest samples of 10 nm, whose particular behavior has been explained in the previous paragraph on the basis of the Ti_2O_3 amount detected in these samples).

Let us focus now on the variation of refractive index with O_2 flow. Figure 16 displays separate plots for the samples with different oxygen flow. For 20, 50 and 100 nm, the samples with a 5 sccm flow rate during deposition have higher refractive index than the samples without oxygen flow, while the 10 nm sample experienced the opposite trend. As it has been explained before, the thinnest samples (10 nm) behavior seems to be strongly affected by the presence of Ti_2O_3 on top of the samples surface, therefore, they will be excluded of the analysis in this paragraph. For the rest of the samples, refractive index is always higher for the samples deposited with O_2 flow, though for the thicker samples TiO_2_G and TiO_2_H , differences are very small. As described in the Supplementary material file, the amount of Ti_2O_3 is always slightly higher for the samples deposited with 5 sccm O_2 flow. Therefore, since the Ti_2O_3 refractive index is always higher than that of TiO_2 [Abdel-Aziz2006], the higher values of the refractive indexes

found for samples deposited with O₂ flow would be partially justified in terms of the higher Ti₂O₃ amount on these samples. Additionally, for the samples deposited with O₂ flow, the O/Ti ratio is slightly higher, which denotes a higher layer density. This fact could also contribute to differences in refractive indexes between samples deposited with and without O₂ flow, and it is attributed to a higher packing density of the layer when appropriate O₂ flow is used [Grayeli Korpi2017].

Figure 16: Refractive index comparison between 0 and 5 sccm samples for a) 10 nm; b) 20 nm c) 50 nm and d) 100 nm

Lastly, Figure 17 gives the extinction coefficients for the samples with Sopra reference values, divided into 2 plots with different magnification. All samples exhibit $k=0$ for wavelengths higher than 350 nm). As can be seen there is no clear trend in the extinction coefficients as a function of thickness but all samples with oxygen flow exhibit higher k values than the samples without it (except for the thinnest one, 10 nm).

Figure 17: Extinction coefficients for TiO₂ samples including the Sopra values (left) and magnification for the wavelength range where k is not zero.

Finally, the appropriateness of the refractive index extracted from ellipsometry data is confirmed by the simulation of the samples transmittance and reflectance and its comparison with experimental results. Figure 18 shows the behavior for all samples. As can be seen the match is very good along the whole spectrum.

Figure 18. Comparison between experimental both reflectance and transmittance data and the simulated functions calculated for all the titanium oxide samples by assuming the n and k values of Figure 14 and 17, respectively.

3.6 Impact on the ARC optimization for multijunction solar cells

In order to evaluate one of the practical impacts of the resulting n and k , we have carried out the optimization of the thicknesses of two broadband anti reflective coating systems for solar cells, namely MgF_2/ZnS (frequently used in lab cells) and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ (mostly used in industry). We have assumed the deposition of these ARCs onto $\text{GaInP}/\text{Ga(In)As}/\text{Ge}$ triple junction solar cells with efficiencies over 40% under 1 sun ($100 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$) AM1.5d spectrum [Barrutia].

Scattering-matrix formalism has been applied to the optimization of ARCs. The generalized matrix method to treat mixed coherent and incoherent multilayers proposed by Centurioni [Centurioni] has been used. The triple junction solar cell is modeled as a multilayer of different semiconductor materials, which can be treated as coherent or incoherent. On top of the solar cell the ARC is modeled as a set of coherent layers. For simplicity we have assumed normal light incidence.

The internal light energy flux and the transmittance in each layer of the solar cell can be calculated from the scattering matrices [Centurioni]. The short circuit current, J_{sc} , of the triple junction is obtained as the minimum one achieved for each sub-cell from their internal quantum efficiency [Valdivia]:

$$J_{sc} = \min \left[q \int \frac{I(\lambda)}{E_{ph}(\lambda)} \cdot T(\lambda) \cdot IQE_n(\lambda) \cdot d\lambda \right]_{n=1}^N \quad (2)$$

where I is the irradiance impinging the device, E_{ph} is the photon energy, T is the ARC transmission, IQE_n is the internal quantum efficiency of the sub-cell m , N is the number of sub-cells (three in our case), λ is the wavelength, and q is the electronic charge.

A software tool has been developed in order to make all the calculations. The objective is to optimize the thickness of the ARC layers, in order to maximize the J_{sc} for the triple junction solar cell. An evolutive algorithm [Vincent] is applied in order to obtain a maximum in the J_{sc} of the sub-cell limiting the overall triple junction solar cell photocurrent.

In the case of the MgF₂/ZnS system we have assumed a fixed 3 nm MgF₂ adhesion layer on top of the solar cell and beneath the ZnS layer. By using the Sopra values, the ARC optimum thicknesses are 3 nm (MgF₂)/93 nm (ZnS)/44 nm (MgF₂) which produces a J_{sc} =14.87 mA/cm² while using the refractive indexes determined in this paper for our real materials the optimum thicknesses are 3 nm (MgF₂)/91 nm (ZnS)/42 nm (MgF₂) which produces a J_{sc} =14.84 mA/cm². The real situation in case that the refractive indexes of deposited materials were not measured, would consist on using the optimum thicknesses for Sopra but combined with the refractive and absorption indexes determined here. In such case, J_{sc} =14.84 mA/cm² is achieved. As expected, no variations are produced because of the very similar values for refractive indexes determined here compared to those of Sopra. Nevertheless, it may be pointed out that the differences found in the ZnS refractive indexes regarding those of Sopra (see Figure 4), especially for wavelengths higher than 900 nm, do not impact the J_{sc} of the triple junction. This is because the Ge subcell, whose QE extends from 900 to 1700 nm, does not limit the J_{sc} of the whole device, so the excess of photocurrent of Ge bottom subcell counterbalance a non-optimum ARC beyond 900 nm. In other words, this triple junction solar cells is highly immune to a non-optimum ARC from 900 to 1800 nm. On the contrary, a higher impact should be expected for quadruple junction solar cells (and with more junctions) where no subcell has an excess of photocurrent so each one could limit the J_{sc} of the whole device and an optimum broadband ARC is required for the whole wavelength range.

In the case of the Al₂O₃/TiO₂, the optimum thicknesses are 84 nm (Al₂O₃)/29 nm (TiO₂) when using the Sopra values which produces a J_{sc} =14.59 mA/cm² while by using the refractive and absorption indexes determined in this paper, the optimum thicknesses are 61 nm (Al₂O₃)/39 nm (TiO₂) which produces a J_{sc} =14.69 mA/cm². The real situation in case that the refractive indexes of deposited materials were not measured, would consist on using the optimum thicknesses calculated for Sopra but combined with the refractive and absorption indexes determined here. In such case, J_{sc} =14.06 mA/cm². Therefore, an increase of 0.63 mA/cm² (4.5% relative) is achieved by determining the real refractive indexes and absorption coefficients of the evaporated materials. This increase would be even higher for quadruple junction solar cells and beyond. These calculations highlight the importance of determining the real optical parameters of the dielectric materials.

4 Summary and Conclusions

In this work, we characterized the thin-film optical properties of MgF₂, ZnS, Ta₂O₅, Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ under a variety of e-beam deposition conditions. For each type of dielectric material multiple layers were deposited at varying thickness and (for oxides) oxygen flow rates by means of tens of EBPVD processes.

By using ellipsometry, the refractive indexes (n) and absorption coefficients (k) as a function of thickness and oxygen flow have been determined and compared to the standard ones of the Sopra database. The differences with the standard Sopra values and the trends with thickness and oxygen flow have been explained by using structural and chemical characterization with XPS, SEM and XRR.

The reflectance (R) and transmittance (T) of samples were measured over the spectrum (300-1800 nm) with spectrophotometry. R and T values were then calculated from the ellipsometry-derived properties using the software *Optical* [Centurioni], and were compared to real measurements from spectrophotometry to evaluate the accuracy of the ellipsometry properties for all samples (all thicknesses and oxygen flows). The obtained sets of optical indexes enabled us to satisfactorily reproduce experimental reflectance, transmittance, and ellipsometry measurements.

The so-obtained sets of n and k of these thin films can be widely applied in multilayer design for the everyday use of these materials in multilayer coatings. As a case study, we have calculated the optimal thicknesses of a Al₂O₃/TiO₂ dual ARC when deposited onto GaInP/Ga(In)As/Ge triple junction solar cells. The use of the refractive indexes and absorption coefficients determined here instead of using those of Sopra, allows a J_{sc} increase of 4.5% (relative). This increase would be even higher for quadruple junctions (and beyond) solar cells.

References

[Algora1997] Carlos Algora del Valle and Manuel Felices Alcaraz, "Performance of Antireflecting Coating-AlGaAs Window Layer Coupling for Terrestrial Concentrator GaAs Solar Cells", IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON ELECTRON DEVICES, VOL. 44, NO. 9, SEPTEMBER 1997

[Burnett1927] Burnett, D. (1927). The Relation between Refractive Index and Density. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 23(8), 907-911. doi:10.1017/S0305004100013773

[Hass1982] G. Hass, J.B. Heaney, W.R. Hunter in "Physics of Thin Films: Advances in Research and Development" Eds. G. Hass, M.H. Francombe, J.L. Vossen, Academic Press 1982

<https://books.google.es/books?id=2pI4BQAAQBAJ&pg=PA48&lpg=PA48&dq=mgf2+water+absorption&source=bl&ots=e-130zzSQf&sig=Tbx5CSERobKQI4essI0SenpBj2U&hl=en&sa=X&ved=0ahUKewix6Y-Zm5XUAhXHvBoKHWz3AaoQ6AEITDAF#v=onepage&q=mgf2%20water%20absorption&f=false>

- [Sarkin2020] A. S. Sarkin, N. Ekren, Ş. Sağlam, A review of anti-reflection and self-cleaning coatings on photovoltaic panels, *Solar Energy* 199, 63-73 (2020).
- [Motamedi2019] M. Motamedi, F. Crisostomo, Y. Yao, S.S. Mofarah, W.-F. Chen, P. Koshy, R.A. Taylor, Single-layer, anti-reflective thin films of porous MgF₂ for solar thermal applications, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* Volume 52, Issue 31, 28 May 2019, Article number 315501.
- [Dumas2000] L. Dumas, E. Quesnel, J.-Y. Robic, Y. Pauleau, Characterization of magnesium fluoride thin films deposited by direct electron beam evaporation, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A* 18(2), 465-469 (2000).
- [Krüger2008] H. Krüger, E. Kemnitz, A. Hertwig, U. Beck, Transparent MgF₂-films by sol-gel coating: Synthesis and optical properties, *Thin Solid Films* 516, 4175-4177 (2008).
- [Sun2020] X. Sun , X. Xu , G. Song , J. Tu, L. Li , P. Yan , W. Zhang, K. Hu, Preparation of MgF₂/SiO₂ coating with broadband antireflective coating by using sol-gel combined with electron beam evaporation, *Optical Materials* 101, 109739 (2020).
- [Krishna2017] A.S.R. Krishna, S.L. Sabat, M.G. Krishna, The design of broad band anti-reflection coatings for solar cell applications, *EPJ Applied Physics* 77 (2017) 10301.
- [Wang2012] W. Wang, A. Freundlich, Optimizing design of 2D sub-wavelength ARC gratings for multi-junction III-V concentrator cells, 38th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (2012) Article number 6318014, 2111-2116.
- [Zhan2014] F. Zhan, Z. Li, X. Shen, H. He, J. Zeng, Design multilayer antireflection coatings for terrestrial solar cells, *The Scientific World Journal* 2014, 265351 (2014).
- [Bernal-Correa2015] R. Bernal-Correa, A. Morales-Acevedo, Á. Pulzara Mora, J. Montes Monsalve, M. López López, Design of Al_xGa_{1-x}As/GaAs/In_yGa_{1-y}As triple junction solar cells with anti-reflective coating, *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing* 37, 57-61 (2015).
- [Herpin] André Herpin, Calcul du pouvoir réflecteur d'un système stratifié quelconque, *Academie des Sciences*, Session 21st July 1947.
- [Aiken] Daniel J. Aiken, High performance anti-reflection coatings for broadband multi-junction solar cells, *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells* 64 (2000) 393-404.

[Dingemans2012] G. Dingemans, W.M.M. Kessels, Status and Prospects of Al₂O₃-Based Surface Passivation Schemes for Silicon Solar Cells, *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A Vacuum Surfaces and Films*, 30(4):040802-040802-27 (2012).

[Centurioni2005] E. Centurioni, Generalized matrix method for calculation of internal light energy flux in mixed coherent and incoherent multilayers, *Appl. Opt.*, 44 (2005) 7532-7539.

[Ianno2010] N.J. Ianno, D.M. Speckman, The effect of deposition conditions on the atomic oxygen induced degradation of MgF₂ anti-reflective coating, 35th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (2010) 5614585, pp. 2546-2549. [10.1109/PVSC.2010.5614585](https://doi.org/10.1109/PVSC.2010.5614585)

[Eiamchai2009] P. Eiamchai, P. Chindaudom, A. Pokaipisit, P. Limsuwan, A spectroscopic ellipsometry study of TiO₂ thin films prepared by ion-assisted electron-beam evaporation, *Curr. Appl. Phys.* 9, 707-712 (2009).

[Abdel-Aziz2006] M.M. Abdel-Aziz, I.S. Yahia, L.A. Wahab, M. Fadel, M.A. Afifi, Determination and analysis of dispersive optical constant of TiO₂ and Ti₂O₃ thin films, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 252 (2006) 8163-8170.

[Adachi1999]

[Atanasova] E. Atanasova, G. Aygun, R. Turan, and Tz. Babeva, "Structural and optical characteristics of tantalum oxide grown by pulsed Nd:YAG laser oxidation", *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A* 24, 206 (2006); <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.2165656>

[Etinger-Geller2019] Y. Etinger-Geller, E. Zoubenko, M. Baskin, L. Kornblum, B. Pokroy, Thickness dependence of the physical properties of atomic-layer deposited Al₂O₃, *J. Appl. Phys.* 125, 185302 (2019).

[Shamala2004] K.S. Shamala, L.C.S. Murthy, K. Narasimha Rao, Studies on optical and dielectric properties of Al₂O₃ thin films prepared by electron beam evaporation and spray pyrolysis method, *Materials Science and Engineering B* 106 (2004) 269–274.

[Madaan2013] Nitesh Madaan, Supriya S. Kanyal, David S. Jensen, Michael A. Vail, Andrew E. Dadson, Mark H. Engelhard, Hussein Samha, Matthew R. Linford, Al₂O₃ e-Beam Evaporated onto Silicon (100)/SiO₂ by XPS, *Surface Science Spectra* 20, 43 (2013); <https://doi.org/10.1116/11.20121102>

[Grayeli Korpi2017] A.R. Grayeli Korpi, S. Rezaee, C. Luna, S. Talu, A. Arman, A. Ahmadpourian, Influence of the oxygen partial pressure on the growth and optical properties of RF-sputtered anatase TiO₂ thin films, *Results in Physics* 7 (2017) 3349-3352.

[Barrutia] Barrutia, L Garcia, I., Barrigón, E., Ochoa, M., Lombardero, I., Hinojosa, M., Caño, P., Bautista, J., Cifuentes, L., Rey-Stolle, I., Algora, C., "Development of the Lattice Matched GaInP/GaInAs/Ge Triple Junction Solar Cell with an Efficiency Over 40%," *2018 Spanish Conference on Electron Devices (CDE)*, 2018, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/CDE.2018.8596996

[Valdivia] Valdivia, C. E., Desfonds, E., Masson, D., Fafard, S., Carlson, A., Cook, J., & Hinzer, K. Optimization of antireflection coating design for multijunction solar cells and concentrator systems. In *Photonics North 2008* (pp. 709915-709915). International Society for Optics and Photonics.

[Vicent] P. Vincent *et al.*, "Alternative approach to optimizing optical spacer layer thickness in solar cell using evolutionary algorithm," *2019 International Conference on Numerical Simulation of Optoelectronic Devices (NUSOD)*, 2019, pp. 89-90, doi: 10.1109/NUSOD.2019.8806865.

[XPSpeak] <https://public.wsu.edu/~scudiero/>

[UNIFIT] <https://www.unifit-software.de/publications.htm>